

E-VOTING SYSTEM FOR UNIVERSITY -TO MANAGE SMALL ASSOCIATION

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Background

Organization and Business Domain

E-Voting System for University is a web-based application that needs to be implemented for casting of votes by the students from anywhere in the world and at any time. The main objective is to provide a system which manages the election activities done in any organization and its calculations in effective manner. This project mainly targets the voting process in University of Sri Jayewardenepura.

Overview of the Existing System

How the existing system functions

There are lot of department associations and clubs within the university. All the associations conduct annual elections for selecting the executive members for their clubs. Currently there is no system for voting. They conduct the voting process manually.

Problems with Existing System

However, there are a lot of drawbacks we could identify such as; People who stay out of the polling area will not be able to cast their votes, Accuracy of the voting process will not be in a considerable level when using a manual system because one person can vote more than one time, high time consumption, frauds in elections, higher cost and lack of confidentiality and data security.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

- People who stay out of the polling area will not be able to cast their votes.
- The existing paper ballot system requires a lot of paper materials and human resources.
- Time consuming and high cost.
- Accuracy of the voting process will not be at a considerable level when using a manual system because one person can vote more than one time.
- If counting votes is done manually, it will be led with human errors. Therefore, result is not accurate.

Requirement Analysis

Functional Requirement

The proposed system meets the following functionalities:

- Login: Allows login to the system only authorized admins and voters.
- Create Poll: Allows system admin to create a poll for the voting, add and register the voters and candidates who are relevant to the poll.
- End Poll: System should automatically end the poll when the system date is equal with the due date (end date) of the poll.
- Post Notices: The system should provide proper features to post information relevant to polls.
- Update/Delete information: Admin can delete or update relevant information.
- Vote: Allows eligible voters to vote for candidates according to the position only one time.

- View result and Report: Allows admin to view selected poll results and can download the PDF version of document.
- Send Email: after system admin register the voters, system should send the credentials for relevant voters.
- Change Password: Voters allow to change their password for their account protection purpose.

Objectives of the proposed system

- To let people cast their votes anytime anywhere.
- To ensures data accuracy during voting processes.
- Minimized time and cost during the voting processes.
- To provide the user-friendly and interactive interfaces and more accurate result with the evidence.

System Development

Development Methodology used

Here I have used waterfall methodology. This is rigid linear model that consists of sequential phase (Synopsis, 2017). This means that any phase in the development process begins only if the previous phase is complete (Tutorialspoint, 2018).

Technologies used

- Client-Side Programming Language: JavaScript, HTML, CSS
- Server-Side Programming Language: PHP
- Database Management System: MySQL
- Integrated Development Environment (IDE): Visual Studio Code
- Interface Development: Bootstrap Framework

Conclusion

E-Voting System for University is a web-based application that is implemented for casting of votes by the students from anywhere in the world and at any time. Currently University of Sri Jayewardenepura conducting paper ballots. However, there are many problems in current system. To address those problems, we have developed the E-voting system. This system mainly develops to manage voting activities in University of Sri Jayewardenepura. However, we can modify this system for corporate organizations as well. We can customize this system according to the client requirements and can provide effective e-voting system for different business organizations. Throughout these customizations and selling we can generate revenue as well.

References

Synopsys (2017) *Software Integrity*. Available at: <https://www.synopsys.com/blogs/software-security/top-4-software-development-methodologies/> (Accessed: 22 April 2020).

Tutorialspoint (2018) *SDLC - Waterfall Model*. Available at: https://www.tutorialspoint.com/sdlc/sdlc_waterfall_model.htm (Accessed: 23 April 2020).